

Surgical Case

Isolated Axillary Tuberculous Lymphadenitis

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A 42-year-old woman presented to me with recent-onset lymph node enlargement in her right axilla. Approximately two months ago, her symptoms began with mild pain and swelling in the right axillary region. The pain was accompanied by fatigue and night sweats. Otherwise, the woman appeared to be in good health.

Upon careful clinical and radiological examination, both breasts appeared normal. Similarly, the neck and the corresponding upper limb appeared clinically and radiologically unaffected. The results of routine blood tests were normal, which further perplexed us.

To resolve the issue definitively, we resorted to an excisional biopsy of one of the axillary lymph nodes. Subsequently, and after gaining clearer insight, we addressed the investigative gap by conducting a radiological study of the chest, which appeared normal.

During surgical exploration, the axillary lymph nodes appeared enlarged with a maximum diameter of 4.5 cm. They were multiple (5 nodes), non-adherent to surrounding structures. Their surface was smooth, with a relatively soft, rubbery yet friable consistency. One node was excised completely, while a second fragmented during removal and was extracted in pieces. The remaining nodes were left in situ. The excised specimen was sent for histopathological examination.

Pathological Diagnosis:

*The pathologist promptly identified the disease pathology as **tuberculous lymphadenitis of the axillary lymph nodes** (see figure below). Subsequently, the patient's file was completed, and she was referred to a Tuberculosis Control Center for treatment.*

العينة : أ. ضخامة عقد لمفية إبطية مستأصلة
ب. خزعات مجزأة من عقدة.

DESCRIPTION OF THE SPECIMEN: A. enlarged lymph node measuring 4.5 cm in greatest dimension. cut sections revealing moderately soft, gray yellowish tissue with focal necrosis.
B. fragments of soft friable tissue with focal necrosis, measuring in total 2 cm.

MICROSCOPIC : A. and B. diffuse granulomatous infiltrate consisting of epithelioid cell granulomas with focal abundant central necrosis, numerous multinucleated giant cells Langhans' type . Slight fibrosis.

CONCLUSION: consistent with Tuberculous Lymphadenitis.
No malignancy.

The Pathology Report

Case Discussion

Extra-pulmonary tuberculosis (EPTB) is not uncommon. Nearly 30% of tuberculous infections manifest as extra-pulmonary disease. Tuberculous lymphadenitis accounts for approximately 43% of extra-pulmonary TB cases. Cervical lymph nodes are the most frequently involved site, followed by axillary lymph nodes (representing 8-20% of all tuberculous lymph node involvements).

In clinical practice when encountering women with isolated axillary lymph node enlargement, most clinicians initially suspect an underlying malignancy in the ipsilateral breast. This diagnostic bias remains justified – indeed, almost an imperative – given the high incidence rates of breast cancer.

Globally, 13% of women develop breast cancer. Conversely, in TB-endemic regions or areas witnessing its resurgence, reported cases of axillary tuberculous lymphadenitis increase significantly. The latter may present either as an isolated axillary lymph node infection or within the spectrum of systemic tuberculous manifestations (pulmonary, osseous, ipsilateral breast involvement, etc.).

*Beyond this, tuberculous involvement of these lymph nodes rises to **second place** in the differential diagnosis of isolated axillary lymphadenopathy in women, and **first place** in men.*

Breast cancer or axillary tuberculous lymphadenitis? The definitive judgment, the definitive judgment, lies with the pathologist. Moreover, both pathologies may coexist within a single axillary lymph node. Is this possible? Yes – such painful particulars have been documented in the medical literature among a rare few unfortunate patients.

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- - [*The Hyperreflexia \(1\), the Pathophysiology of Hyperactivity*](#)
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- - [*The Hyperreflexia \(3\), the Pathophysiology of Extended Hyperreflex*](#)
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 - *The Nerve Transmission through Neural Fiber (2), The Action Potentials*

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 - *The Function of Standard Action Potentials & Currents*

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DOI *The Sensory Receptors*

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